

Capstone Project

Nigeria Youths in Politics: A Sustainable Model for Youth Civic Engagement and Leadership Development

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Executive Summary

Nigeria has over 58% of its citizens under the age of 30 and a median age of 18.1 years. According to the 2006 census, the youthful population constituted almost 60% of the population. Odoh, R. H. E., & Eme, O. I. (2014). Yet young Nigerians (ages 18–30) remain systematically excluded from governance and policymaking. Despite the 2018 "Not Too Young to Run" Act, only 20% of youth are registered political party members, and minimal youth representation exists in the National Assembly. This exclusion creates a dangerous disconnect: policies are designed without input from the majority population they serve.

Nigeria Youths in Politics (NYP) is a social enterprise addressing this gap through a 6-week civic engagement program. We provide policy training, mentorship with political leaders, and direct pathways to governance for young Nigerians aged 18 to 30. Our competitive advantage lies in creating actionable opportunities, not just education, but real access to decision-making processes.

With over 133 million potential participants and pricing at ₦5,000 per person, NYP targets 100 youth in our pilot program, scaling to 1000 annually. We seek ₦1 million in initial funding to launch operations, develop curriculum, and execute marketing campaigns. Success will be measured through 80% attendance rates, 50% increases in governance confidence, and measurable graduate placement in policy roles, ultimately building a pipeline of informed leaders transforming Nigeria's democratic future.

Section 1: Introduction

1.1 Overview:

Nigeria Youth in Politics (NYP) is a social enterprise designed to improve Nigeria's youth's political participation. With 58% of Nigeria's population under age 30, young people remain systematically excluded from governance and policymaking despite representing the demographic most affected by policy decisions. NYP addresses this disconnect through a comprehensive 6-week civic engagement program that provides policy training, mentorship with political leaders, and direct pathways to governance for young Nigerians aged 18 to 30.

Our competitive advantage lies in creating practical opportunities and real access to decision-making platforms in Politics. Unlike our competitors that focus solely on advocacy or general leadership training, NYP creates pathways for youth to engage with state leaders, influence policy discussions, and secure roles in government.

NYP is currently in its **research and development stage**. We are actively developing our program curriculum, conducting competitive analysis against similar initiatives (such as YIAGA Africa, Learn Politics and LEAP Africa), and incorporating feedback for maximum impact.

This business plan outlines our current progress, operational framework, and strategic roadmap for the next 6 to 12 months as we transition from development to pilot implementation and eventual market entry. Our immediate focus is finalising curriculum content, establishing partnerships with universities and state government stakeholders, and executing our inaugural 6-week program with 100 participants across Nigeria.

Progress to Date:

- Program Validation: Pilot workshops and collected feedback to refine content and delivery.
- Completed initial market research and competitive analysis
- Defined target audience and value proposition

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- Drafted curriculum framework focused on policy training, civic engagement, and mentorship
- Identified key partnership opportunities with educational institutions and government stakeholders
- Secured commitment from four experienced speakers and mentors

What Has Spurred This Business Plan:

The urgency of Nigeria's youth exclusion from governance has become increasingly evident. Recent protests across Kenya, Tanzania, and other African nations demonstrate that young people are ready to demand change, but they need the skills, networks, and platforms to channel that energy into sustainable transformation.

This business plan outlines the next phase of development, including Curriculum refinement, executing our pilot program, and demonstrating proof of concept that will enable us to scale our impact across Nigeria and eventually other African nations. NYP to capitalise on this moment of heightened youth political consciousness.

1.2 Vision Statement:

To see an increased level of participation in politics and Government by Nigerian youths.

1.3 Mission Statement:

To reduce the age gap in governance and ensure that more Nigerian youths actively participate in politics and policymaking through civic education, leadership training, and direct engagement with key decision-makers.

1.4 Research Aim:

To understand the current state of youth political participation in Nigeria, this research will examine how actively young Nigerians engage in politics, the barriers they face, their interest in becoming involved, and their willingness to pay for solutions offered by NYP. It will also assess how NYP's civic engagement model can address these gaps and create practical pathways for stronger youth participation.

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1.5 Objectives:

1. Enrol and train 100 young Nigerians (ages 18-30) in our inaugural 6-week civic engagement program by Month 6 (June 2026), achieving an 80% completion rate and 75% positive feedback rating.
2. Connect at least 50 program graduates (10% of the cohort) with mentorships, internships, or advisory positions with state leaders and policy organisations within 3 months post-program completion (Month 9).
3. Generate ₦5 million in Year 1 revenue through participant fees (₦2.5M) and grants/partnerships (₦2.5M), reaching operational break-even by Month 18 (December 2026).

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Figure 1.0 Business Model Canvas

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Figure 1.1 Marketing Model Canvas

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NYP OBJECTIVES

Objectives	SMART	Description
Establish NYP as a Recognized Civic Engagement Platform	Specific	Launch and successfully execute our inaugural 6-week civic engagement program
	Measurable	Enroll and train 500 young Nigerians (ages 18-30) with 80% completion rate
	Achievable	Leverage partnerships with universities and social media campaigns to recruit participants
	Relevant	Position NYP as a credible platform for youth political training in Nigeria
	Time-Bound	Complete first cohort by Month 6
Build Direct Pathways to Governance for Program Graduates	Specific	Create concrete opportunities for youth to engage with political leaders and secure governance roles
	Measurable	Connect at least 50 graduates (10% of cohort) with mentorship relationships, internships, or advisory positions with state leaders or policy organizations
	Achievable	Leverage partnerships with state governments and policy experts established during program delivery
	Relevant	Demonstrates tangible impact beyond training, proving NYP creates real access to decision-making
	Time-Bound	Track placements within 3 months post-program completion (Month 9)
Achieve Financial Sustainability Through Diversified Revenue	Specific	Generate revenue through participant fees, grants, and partnerships to cover operational costs
	Measurable	Achieve ₦5 million in Year 1 revenue (₦2.5 million from participant fees at ₦5,000 per person for 500 participants; ₦2.5 million from grants/partnerships)
	Achievable	Affordable pricing ensures accessibility while grants supplement costs
	Relevant	Financial sustainability enables program scalability and long-term impact
	Time-Bound	Reach break-even by Month 18 (December 2026)

Figure 1.2
NYP SMART Objective

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1.6 The Value Proposition

Nigeria Youth in Politics offers a comprehensive, youth-centred solution that directly addresses the systemic barriers preventing young Nigerians from participating in governance. Its core value propositions include:

- A Direct pathway to political engagement, not just theoretical training, connecting youth with state leaders, mentorship opportunities, and real governance roles that most civic programs fail to provide.
- Practical, actionable curriculum designed by young Nigerians who understand the barriers firsthand, covering policy analysis, citizen engagement, public speaking, and grassroots organising skills immediately applicable to political participation.
- Affordable and accessible at ₦5,000 per participant, ensuring that financial constraints don't prevent interested youth.
- Mentorship model connecting participants directly with experienced political leaders, policymakers, and governance experts who provide guidance, open doors, and help navigate Nigeria's complex political landscape.
- A scalable framework that enables future expansion across Nigeria and other African nations facing similar challenges of youth exclusion from governance, with the potential to train thousands of young leaders annually.

Section 2: The Product/ Service:

2.1 The Product/ Service Model

Nigeria Youth in Politics operates as a civic engagement training program delivered through a structured 6-week curriculum that combines in-person workshops, mentorship sessions, and practical engagement opportunities. The program consists of:

- Civic Training and Education: Structured workshops covering practical political skills, including policy analysis, public speaking, grassroots organising, and citizen engagement. Content is delivered by experienced facilitators and tailored specifically to Nigeria's political landscape, addressing the knowledge gap identified in our research where young people report "not knowing where to start" in politics.
- Mentorship with Political Leaders: Direct access to experienced political leaders, policymakers, and governance experts through structured one-on-one and group mentorship sessions. This addresses the barrier of "not knowing anyone in politics", a challenge cited by 60% of surveyed youth as preventing their political participation (Nigeria Youth Political Participation Survey, 2024).
- Direct Pathways to Governance: Unlike programs that only offer training, NYP creates concrete opportunities through partnerships with state governments and policy organisations, connecting graduates with internships, advisory positions, and mentorship roles. This feature was validated through stakeholder interviews, where political leaders expressed willingness to mentor trained youth but noted the absence of structured programs to facilitate such connections.

2.2 Meeting the Needs of the Customer

Of the Nigerians surveyed aged 18–30 (n=113), **30.6%**, the largest group, felt that their voices would not make a difference, reflecting apathy and discouragement toward political participation. **21.6%** reported safety and security concerns as their reason for disengagement. **11.6%** cited limited access to political leaders, while **14.4%** pointed to the absence of a clear pathway into government.

NYP would address these barriers, as stated in the table below:

Table 2.0 maps the core challenges faced in the primary data of Nigeria Youth in Politics

Customer Need/PainPoint	NYP Solution	Validated by
Lack of a clear pathway to enter governance.	A Direct pathway to political engagement, not just theoretical training, connecting youth with state leaders, mentorship opportunities, and real governance roles that most civic programs fail to provide.	14.4% of Nigerian Youths stated a lack of clear pathway to get involved in Governance
Lack of technical know-how or relevant skills to participate in government.	Practical, actionable curriculum covering policy analysis, citizen engagement, public speaking, and grassroots organising skills immediately applicable to political participation.	11.7% of respondents stated that they lack knowledge about governance and public policy.

Section 3: Industry and Market Analysis:

3.1 Opportunity: According to national demographic data, young Nigerians aged 18–30 make up over 58% of the population, representing a potential market size of more than 133 million individuals. This is a large target market. Out of 112 surveyed youths, 91.1% stated not being part of a formal political party or youth political movement, with only 8.9% actively involved (Nigeria Youth Political Participation Survey, 2025).

Given that political party membership is a prerequisite for meaningful political engagement in Nigeria, this 91.1% represents an untapped market of young Nigerians who are excluded from governance despite being the demographic majority. NYP seeks to address this by equipping youth with the needed civic skills, mentorships, as well as pathways to Involvement in Government

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Are you a dues-paying or registered member of any formal political party or youth political movement?

112 responses

Figure 3.0: Number of Nigerian Youths Actively Involved in Political Parties

3.2 Market Analysis

Nigeria Youth in Politics operates within the **civic engagement** and **social impact** sector. Notable players in this space include:

1. Learn Politics: A civic learning LTD/GTE organisation that simplifies complex governance and democracy concepts for everyday Nigerians.
2. Yiaga Africa: A Nigerian nonprofit promoting participatory democracy, human rights, and civic engagement, with a strong focus on youth.
3. LEAP Africa: A nonprofit that equips young people with the skills and mindset needed to become ethical leaders through training, publications, and e-learning.

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3.3 Industry Viability and Growth Potential

Civic engagement is on the rise, especially amongst young people. Gen Zs are leading a silent revolution and seeking to get more involved in Government. However, aside from digital engagement and advocacy, there is a need to translate to real-life engagement, which demonstrates a need for NYP's offerings. African youth are no longer content to remain on the sidelines. They are demanding a voice in shaping their future. Briggs and Briggs (2024)

3.4 Government Support and Policy Environment

In May 2018, the Nigerian government passed the Not Too Young to Run Act, reducing the age limits for various elective offices (e.g., from 40 to 35 for President; from 30 to 25 for House of Representatives). This shows strong government support and policy alignment with the goals of Nigeria Youths in Politics.

3.5 Target Market and Segmentation

The primary market for the Nigerian Youth in Politics is approximated to be 133 million People. Nigeria's population of more than 230 million are youths: The median age is 18.1 years, and 58% of the population is under age 30 (Worldometer, 2025; World Bank, 2023a). The secondary market includes Civic organisations, NGOs, and government stakeholders who are interested in youth engagement.

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3.6 Market Size (Volume and Value)

Figure 3.1 Nigeria Youths in Politics Market Segmentation

3.7 SWOT Analysis

Figure 3.2 Nigeria Youths in Politics SWOT Analysis

The **SWOT** analysis of NYP reveals it's a **strong contender** in creating real practical access and pathways to Governance for Youths. This was revealed during the Qualitative Interview of [Dr Emmanuel](#) (Nigeria Youth in Politics Interview, 2025). The major support young people lack that prevents them from participating in politics includes lack of information, political apathy, feeling their voice doesn't matter, and NYP solves that with its services

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provided, such as direct pathway guidance, mentorship provision, and civic training to get skills for political participation.

Opportunities lie in not just being a civic training program like competitors such as Learn Politics and Yiaga Africa, but also in providing practical actionable pathway access for youths in politics.

Weaknesses identified according to the qualitative interview of [Great Owete](#) include creating something accessible for rural communities in Nigeria, rural youths with little to no access to digital tools, internet, or money to pay for services offered, and service cost (Nigeria Youth in Politics Interview, 2025). **Threats** are sustainability and financial willingness, as other competitors are heavily subsidized as well as funded by grants/funders.

Section 4: Competition

4.1 Market Competition

The Market Competitors of Nigeria Youths in Politics include: Yiaga Africa, Learn Politics, LEAP Africa

Organization	NYP	Yiaga Africa	Learn Politics	LEAP Africa
Service	Practical political pathway access, mentorship, civic training for real participation	Civic engagement, election monitoring, youth advocacy	Simplified civic and governance lessons for everyday Nigerians	Youth leadership development, ethics training, mentorship
Market share	Emerging player, growing awareness	Strong national presence	Still growing its audience	Well-established across Africa
Growth	High growth potential due to Gen Z interest in governance	Steady growth backed by grants and partnerships	Growing through digital adoption	Consistent growth through donor-funded programs
Target audience	Youths aged 18–30 seeking real political pathways	Youth advocates, activists, civic-minded citizens	Young Nigerians seeking basic civic knowledge	Young leaders, students, emerging professionals
Price structure	#5000	Mostly free (grant-funded)	Free or low-cost online content	Free training, subsidized youth programs

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Marketing strategies	Universities Campaigns, Social media, and community engagement	Advocacy campaigns, partnerships, nationwide programs	Social media education, influencer-style civic content	Leadership programs, alumni networks, school partnerships
Strengths	Practical political access, mentorship, personalized guidance	Strong credibility, wide reach, recognized brand	Easy-to-understand and civic content	Long-standing reputation, strong training programs
Weaknesses	Limited funding, not friendly to rural communities.	Dependent on donor funding	Limited practical political pathways	Focus mostly on leadership, not political pathways
Key advantage	Unique focus on real, actionable political entry pathways for youth	Established presence and policy influence	Simple civic education for beginners	Strong leadership development ecosystem

4.2 Potential New Entrants

The probability of new entrants into this space is moderate to high, as more civic organizations are emerging to meet the rising interest of Gen Zs who want to get more involved in politics and governance. Potential new competitors include youth-focused civic learning platforms, NGOs, digital training startups, and advocacy groups that may see opportunities in political education and youth engagement.

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Are you currently registered to vote?

112 responses

4.3 Barriers to Entry

The barrier to entry in this sector is high. New entrants must deal with major challenges such as funding limitations, sustainability planning, trust-building, gaining users, and proving their credibility in a space where politics is not something that generally excites or motivates many young Nigerians. There is also the challenge of content development, partnerships, community building, and establishing actionable pathways, not just training. These are significant barriers that new organizations must overcome.

4.4 Switching Costs

The cost for a customer to switch to competitors is low because civic content and training are widely available, and many competitors offer free or subsidized

programs. This means users can easily move from one platform to another unless there is a unique value proposition.

Section 5: Operations Plan

5.1 Legal and Licensing Requirements

To operate, NYP does not require patents because it is not producing a technical invention or proprietary product. However, it will require:

1. **Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) registration** as an LTD/GTE or NGO
2. **SCUML registration**, depending on revenue structure
3. **Tax Identification Number (TIN)**
4. **Permits for hosting physical events**, where required
5. **Data protection compliance** (Nigeria Data Protection Regulation – NDPR), since user information will be collected through sign-ups and training programs

These licences allow NYP to operate legally while working with youth, government stakeholders, and partners.

5.2 Operational Resources

NYP requires a mix of physical and human resources to deliver its services:

Physical & Digital Assets

1. Laptops, phones, and tablets
2. Internet access and digital tools
3. Training materials (handbooks, templates, workbooks)
4. Co-working or training space for physical sessions
5. Audio-visual equipment for virtual sessions (microphones, lighting, Zoom/Google Meet setup)
6. Productivity software (Microsoft Office, Google Workspace)
7. Learning Management System (LMS) for structured training

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5.3 Intangible Resources

1. Specialized knowledge in civic education, governance, public policy, and political pathways
2. Mentorship network of verified policymakers and governance actors
3. Training curriculum, documents, and frameworks developed internally
4. Certification and credibility, which increases trust among youth
5. Brand reputation built through consistent value and high-quality programming

Acquisition Method:

These will be secured through **direct purchase**, partnerships, and in some cases, **donations or sponsorships** from civic and private organisations.

Human Resources

1. Governance trainers and policy experts
2. Mentors (senior policymakers, public servants, legislative aides, political leaders)
3. Program manager
4. Communications and social media lead
5. Facilitators for both online and offline sessions
6. Volunteers for community engagement

Acquisition Method: Through recruitment, partnerships, and external facilitators engaged on a per-program basis.

Service Delivery Method

NYP's services will be delivered in a structured pipeline from the production point to the consumption point:

1. **Content Development:** Creating civic training modules, mentorship guides, templates, and policy analysis toolkits.

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2. **Program Delivery**
 - Hybrid model (virtual + in-person sessions)
 - Training sessions, direct mentorship, internships, and civic engagement opportunities
3. **Customer Delivery**
 - Youths access programs through online registration
 - Attend weekly sessions for 6 weeks
 - Receive mentorship, join peer-learning groups, and access tools
 - Program completion → certificate + recommendations + network access
4. **Follow-up and Community Engagement**
 - Alumni network, WhatsApp groups, policy forums, referral systems

This ensures NYP supports participants before, during, and after each cohort.

Suppliers

1. ICT suppliers for digital devices
2. Printing vendors for training materials
3. Co-working spaces or event centres for physical training
4. Software providers (Zoom, Canva, Google Workspace)

The relationship will be maintained through long-term vendor agreements, timely payments, and continuous purchasing.

5.4 Management Plan

Leadership: The project will be led by me, drawing on my background in policy research, civic engagement, and project coordination. I bring experience from institutions like the Tony Blair Institute and have worked directly with government partners and youth-focused organisations. My passion for youth empowerment and governance drives this mission.

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Personnel Plan

In the first year, I plan to hire a small, agile team that includes:

1. Program Coordinator to manage training and mentorship logistics
2. Content Creator/Social Media Lead to handle campaigns and storytelling
3. Community Engagement Officer to coordinate with student ambassadors and youth leaders.

Key Partners / Distributors

1. Civic organisations (Yiaga Africa, LEAP Africa, Connected Development)
2. University student associations
3. NYSC community development groups
4. Government ministries, agencies, state governments
5. NGOs running leadership and governance programs
6. Policy experts and public leaders who serve as mentors

These partners help distribute NYP's programs, expand reach, and strengthen credibility.

Distribution channels include:

1. Social media (TikTok, Instagram, X, WhatsApp)
2. University clubs and student bodies
3. Community groups
4. Email newsletters
5. Partnerships and speaking engagements

Section 6: Marketing And Sales Plan

6.1 Customer Awareness Strategy

Nigeria Youth in Politics (NYP) will adopt a mixed marketing strategy, both onsite and online. NYP will raise awareness online through digital and social media platforms, as young people in Nigeria spend most of their time online. Awareness will be driven through Instagram, TikTok, X, YouTube, and WhatsApp community groups, and offline through universities, active student leaders across campuses, as well as students interested in political involvement.

Figure 6.0 NYP segmented promotion strategy

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6.2 Product Promotion Strategy

NYP will promote its programs and services through:

1. Campus outreach to mobilise young people.
2. Focus group meetings with student leaders, youth influencers, and political clubs.
3. Workshops, seminars, and training sessions on civic engagement and leadership.
4. Radio and TV talk show appearances to discuss youth participation.
5. Strategic presentations to NGOs, youth councils, and political advocacy groups.
6. Partnerships with student unions, youth organisations, and civil society groups.

6.3 Pricing Assumptions:

- 32% of surveyed students (n=112) indicated willingness to participate in our program if it were free. But 68% indicated willingness to pay some amount. Hence, Most NYP activities will be paid for or low-cost to ensure accessibility to young Nigerians.

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If a 6-week program offered high-quality training and direct mentorship with state leaders, what is the maximum fee you would be willing to pay for access? (Select one)

112 responses

Figure 6.1 Willingness to Pay for NYP Services. Most students were willing to pay.

Incentives to Attract and Retain Participants

Networking opportunities with political leaders

6.4 Distribution Channels

NYP's services will reach young people through:

Digital Channels

1. Website for registrations, resources, and learning materials.
2. WhatsApp and Telegram communities for engagement.
3. Social media platforms for campaigns and mobilisation.

Offline Channels

1. Universities and colleges
2. Youth centres and community hubs
3. Partner organisations, NGOs, and student associations

Section 7: Financial Plan

7.1 Key Assumptions

- All financial estimates are calculated in **Nigerian Naira (₦)** and based on current market prices as of **Q1 2025**.
- NYP will charge a **participation fee of ₦5,000** (or slightly higher depending on the city) for youth trainees.
- To ensure **full accessibility for youths who cannot afford the fee**, at least **40% of participants** will be sponsored through scholarships funded by partners, donors, and institutional grants.
- NYP will continue operating with a hybrid model (physical + virtual trainings), which will help reduce venue and logistics costs in the first year.
- Grants and partnerships are assumed to remain the primary source of funding in Year 1 while the fee-paying model grows over time.
- No tax is expected in Year 1 due to NYP operating as a youth-centred non-profit initiative.

7.2 Funding Required

To successfully launch the pilot phase of Nigeria Youth in Politics (NYP), we require a total of **₦1,000,000**. This funding will cover core expenses such as program development, training materials, facilitator fees, partnerships, digital infrastructure, and initial marketing and outreach efforts. The funds will enable us to run the first cohort, measure impact, and establish credibility for future scale and investment.

Use of Funds	Estimated Cost (Naira #)
Program Development & Training Materials	300,000
Facilitator & Mentorship Costs	300,000
Logistics & Operations	200,000

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Marketing & Digital Infrastructure	200,000
Total	1,000,000

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7.1 Funding Sources

To raise this fund, we would explore these sources:

Funding Source	Amount (₦)	Strategy
Participation Fees (100 students @ ₦5,000 each)	500,000	Cost for participation
Grants from Civic/Youth-Focused Organisations	400,000	Applications to Grants for Civic and Youth Organisations
Sponsorship/Partnership Support	100,000	Money to be gotten from Partners (Media, etc.)

Figure 7.2 Funding sources for NYP

Category	Description	Estimated Users
Total Addressable Market (TAM)	All Nigerian youths aged 18–30 who are interested in politics	133,000,000
Serviceable Available Market (SAM)	Youths in cities and towns who have access to the internet and want to learn about politics	40,000,000
Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)	0.5% of SAM who are likely to use NYP in the first phase	20,000,000

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Table 7.3 Market Segmentation and Monetisation Estimates

7.2 Financial Statements (Appendix A)

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1lzY-1XiDb6SjWAPPARj5uIAEbQYT9YyHpyr9SsvVa8g/edit?usp=sharing>

Table 7.4 Action Plan

Timeline	Activity	Responsible	Deliverable
Month 1	Finalise funding, partnerships & sponsors Complete curriculum design & training modules Build website + learning portal	Founder + Partnerships Lead Program Director + Curriculum Team Tech Lead	Funding commitments + signed partner onboarding letters NYP Civic & Political Literacy Curriculum (v1) Website + registration portal live
Month 2	Recruit facilitators, mentors & volunteers Branding & marketing rollout Open participant applications (N5,000 fee + free slots)	Operations Lead Marketing Lead Admin Team	15–20 facilitators and mentors onboarded Social media campaign + flyers + visibility assets 300+ applications received
Month 3	Run the first cohort of workshops across 2–3 states Provide scholarship access to low-income youths	Program Team + Facilitators Finance + Partnerships Lead M&E Lead	150–200 youths trained 40% participants sponsored Initial impact report (Cohort

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	Collect feedback (surveys + interviews)		1)
Month 4	<p>Launch mentorship program,</p> <p>Improve curriculum using Cohort 1 feedback</p> <p>Prepare advanced leadership modules</p>	<p>Mentorship Coordinator</p> <p>Curriculum Team</p> <p>Program Director</p>	<p>100 youths matched with political mentors</p> <p>Updated content (v2)</p> <p>Advanced political leadership toolkit (v1)</p>
Month 5-6	<p>Begin institutional partnerships (universities, CSOs)</p> <p>Mid-year M&E + financial review</p>	<p>Partnerships Lead</p> <p>Founder + M&E Team</p>	<p>3–5 partnership MOUs</p> <p>Progress report + budget accountability</p>

Section 8: Research Methodology And Recommendations

8.1 Approach

Objective: This cross-sectional study aimed to evaluate the involvement of young Nigerians in politics, their desire for a solution, and their readiness to pay for such solutions. The study also explored how NYP could help increase youth participation in politics in Nigeria.

Method: This study used a mixed-methods approach, combining a student survey (n = 112) and semi-structured interviews (n = 7) young leaders, political leaders, and civic organization leaders. The research was guided by the Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM) framework.

8.2 Data Collection Process

- A structured survey was distributed to young Nigerians via Google Forms on social media. The survey collected data on age, gender, level of participation in

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- politics in Nigeria, confidence level in political participation, the biggest challenge preventing political engagement, the support needed that would be most helpful to increase political participation, as well as willingness to pay for solutions.
- In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with seven political leaders (both young and experienced leaders), transcribed, and analyzed using Braun & Clarke’s (2006) thematic analysis method. Themes were manually coded and verified across transcripts. Participants were selected using purposive sampling and provided informed consent. Interviews explored personal experiences with political participation, limitations that youths face, proposed solutions, and feedback on NYP’s proposed interventions.
- **Validation:** A pilot workshop was conducted to test the program offering. The curriculum was taught, and feedback was collected to refine both content and delivery.

Age (18-30)

112 responses

Figure 8.0 Respondents by Age Group (N=112). The majority of participants were between the ages of 18-30 (76.8%), while 23.2% were 30 years and above.

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Are you a dues-paying or registered member of any formal political party or youth political movement?

112 responses

Figure 8.1 Respondents who are members of a political party (N=112), which tells the number involved in Politics.

8.3 Limitations

The study was limited to an online survey, as I was in Rwanda and could not physically sample Nigerian youths in Nigeria. This may have excluded perspectives from individuals with limited internet access or those in rural areas.

Mitigation:

Future phases will include in-person surveys, focus groups, and outreach in multiple Nigerian regions to ensure broader representation.

8.4 Key Findings

Many Nigerian youths feel their voices do not matter, leading to strong apathy toward political participation shared [Emmanuel](#), the political leaders, think, Youths are lazy, don't want to do the hard work. They don't want to start small from a local

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government chairman level, but from the top, presidential level, Governor level. The political leaders feel a lot of elders want to mentor the youths, the youths feel they don't have anything to learn from the leaders, as they don't approve of their lifestyle shared [Ndanusa](#), Equally, [Victoria Kintan](#), Founder of Learn Politics, expressed advice for Nigerian youths in Politics to collaborate with already existing Civic Organisations for more efficiency also a reluctance for youths to pay for civic programs except it's subsidies that helped with market research.

1. **Mentorship and Political Guidance:**

Political leaders expressed willingness to mentor youths, but young people often feel they have little to learn from current leaders due to disapproval of their lifestyles or leadership style cited Dr Clarence Moniba. Mentorship opportunities exist but are largely at family or elite levels, not broadly accessible.

2. **Capacity and Political Knowledge:**

Youths lack understanding of the political system, the constitution, stakeholder engagement, and collaboration skills. Many do not know how to navigate political structures effectively or build coalitions across parties.

3. **Ethical Leadership Needs:**

There is a shortage of ethical leaders. Current leadership is often transactional, tribal, or self-serving. Youths need exposure to ethical leadership models, guided by values like fairness, compassion, and integrity.

4. **Financial Barriers:**

Participation in politics requires significant financial resources, which limits youth involvement. Most youths are unwilling or unable to fund their political engagement independently.

5. **Collaboration and Grassroots Engagement:**

Youths need to start at the local level, collaborate across age groups, and

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leverage existing civic organisations to build influence and gain experience. Programs must be designed with rural contexts in mind and include mentorship, skill-building, and political literacy.

6. Pathways and Motivation:

Successful political participation often requires starting small, volunteering, building networks, and gradually climbing the political ladder. Passion, ethical guidance, and practical mentorship are key drivers of sustained engagement.

7. Payment and Program Participation:

While youths see the value of civic programs, there is general reluctance to pay for participation unless subsidies or financial support are provided.

As illustrated in **Figure 8.2**, young Nigerians participate in politics at varying levels of frequency.

How often do you engage in political or civic activities (e.g., following debates, attending town halls, advocating online)?

112 responses

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Figure 8.3 illustrates that young Nigerians are more involved in online political participation (such as social media advocacy) compared to offline, on-the-ground engagement.

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Figure 8.4 illustrates young Nigerians' confidence levels in analysing government policy documents or recommending policy changes. This finding validates the concern that many young people feel insufficiently equipped with the skills needed for meaningful political engagement.

Please rate your confidence in your ability to analyze a government policy document and propose a change.

112 responses

As illustrated in **Figure 8.5**, the perception that their voices would not be heard prevents many youths from engaging in political activities.

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What is the single biggest challenge preventing your political engagement? (Select one)

111 responses

Figure 8.6 shows that out of 112 participants, 62 responded that practical governance training would be the most helpful for getting started in politics and increasing youth political participation. Additionally, 50 participants highlighted interning or volunteering in government offices, and 45 emphasised the value of direct mentorship with political leaders.

Which of the following support options would be most helpful to increase your political participation? (Select up to 2)

112 responses

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If a 6-week program offered high-quality training and direct mentorship with state leaders, what is the maximum fee you would be willing to pay for access? (Select one)

112 responses

Figure 8.7 shows the willingness of Nigerian youths to pay for solutions that support youth participation in politics. Only 32.1% stated they would participate if the solutions were free, while the remaining majority are willing to pay.

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If the program offered a payment plan (e.g., pay in two or three instalments), would that make you more likely to participate?

112 responses

8.5 Conclusion

Youth participation in Nigerian politics is still low because of apathy, limited knowledge, financial challenges, and few mentorship opportunities. NYP's approach of mentorship, practical training, and starting at the grassroots level helps fill these gaps and gives young Nigerians a real pathway to get involved in politics.

8.6 Recommendations / Next Steps

NYP should expand its reach to different states and include rural areas. It should work closely with civic organisations and political leaders to provide mentorship. Programs should be affordable and accessible. Youths should be encouraged to start small at local government levels and build experience over time.

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8.7 Call to Action

Nigerian youths need to take the first step, collaborate with others, and actively participate in politics. Experienced leaders, mentors, and organisations should support them to ensure the next generation leads with ethics, knowledge, and real impact.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Qualitative and Quantitative Interview Materials

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1hFLe9NRDRgqsR8oGG7fMwespLmgnAxb5?usp=sharing>

Appendix B: Reference Videos

1. Youth Political Participation in Nigeria –

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- https://youtu.be/U50n4nsY_d0?si=4oBtrHJ8MgjYTCn8
2. Why Nigerian Youths Struggle in Politics –
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOGXoj6olU0>
 3. Empowering Young Nigerians in Governance –
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h6uqpxXfdhI>

Appendix C: Supporting Academic Resource

- *Youth Inclusion and Political Participation in Nigeria's 2023 Election* –
https://ijhssm.org/issue_dcp/Youth%20Inclusion%20And%20Political%20Participation%20In%20Nigeria%20s%202023%20Election.pdf